

Adopting Remedial Measures in The Absence of Laboratory Equipment: Narratives of Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) Teachers

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Abstract. This study unwrapped teachers' experiences in adopting remedial measures without laboratory equipment for effective learning in secondary schools of the Digos City Division. Ten (10) teachers applied remedial measures to address the absence of laboratory equipment in teaching and participated in the study. This study used a phenomenological approach to extract the participants' ideas. The virtual in-depth interview was employed to gather some information regarding their respective narratives as they adopted remedial measures in the absence of laboratory equipment in teaching. The thematic analysis of the responses from the participants of the study revealed the experiences of teachers in the absence of laboratory equipment. It delved into lack of learning equipment, lack of training in areas of specialization, and unprepared equipment due to lack of budget. However, the teachers employed the following coping mechanisms: being optimistic despite setbacks, becoming technologically savvy, and contextualizing learning instructions. The insight drawn from the study's findings was contingencies for instructional facilities and teaching strategies that develop teacher's expertise. These findings may create a training program focusing on creative teaching strategies, improvisation techniques, and technology integration to better prepare educators to adapt to unexpected challenges. Additionally, establishing a culture of collaboration and knowledge sharing among teachers fosters resilience and innovation in problem-solving.

KEY WORDS

1. absences of laboratory equipment
2. adopting remedial measure
3. technologically savvy

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1. Introduction

Education is a must for individuals considering the educational system's problems, trends, and innovations. Considering the global environment, people view education not only as a way of developing people skills but also as preparing our students to be globally competitive. If the schools were able to produce quality graduates, it would redound on the quality of work they would provide in their workplaces. Adopting remedial measures without laboratory equipment presents several challenges educators must navigate to ensure effective teaching and learning experiences. One significant issue is its limitation on hands-on learning opportunities, which are crucial for reinforcing theoretical concepts and fostering practical skills

development in subjects like science and technology. Without access to laboratory equipment, students may miss out on valuable experiential learning experiences, hindering their ability to fully grasp complex scientific principles. A major obstacle to effective science education in Liberia, as in many developing countries, is the lack of laboratory equipment. Students frequently lack access to necessary tools for hands-on experimentation, especially in resource-constrained locations and schools, which impairs their comprehension of scientific topics. Teachers and legislators have struggled with this issue, looking for substitute teaching strategies to make up for the equipment shortage. Educators creatively utilize everyday materials or low-cost alternatives to simulate laboratory experiments. Ministry of Education's (2019) and the World Bank's (2020) Many scholars who specialize in education policy reform have identified the exclusion of stakeholders, inadequate resource allocation, faulty data, a lack of political will, a lack of capacity and technical expertise, inadequate monitoring and assessment, and centralized governance as contributing to poor policy outcomes (European Union, 2020). ASER (2019) reports that by the time they turn ten years old, more than fifty percent of Indian youngsters are unable to read and comprehend a simple text. Just six out of ten children will finish secondary education by 2030, and one in six children will still not be enrolled in primary and secondary education, per recent studies on children who are not in school (UNESCO, 2019). In addition, in situations where actual equipment is unavailable, educators can convey scientific concepts through models, movies, and demonstrations. Collaborative activities and project-based learning strategies are also used to help students apply scientific knowledge to common resources. Though they provide some respite, these methods fall short of the educational opportunities provided by well-equipped laboratories Wehye, B. Y. (2023).

In the Philippines, Technology and Livelihood Education intends to develop knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes that will prepare the students for entry into the world of work. This will enable the students to gain understanding and acquire competencies in various activities as they relate to Home Economics, Agriculture Arts, Industrial Arts, and Entrepreneurship. The programs of vocational education in this country are provided for in Act Number 3377, otherwise known as the Vocational Act of 1927. Article XIV, Section 5 of the 1935 Philippine Constitution, also provides for the development of vocational efficiency. Regional Memorandum No. 233, s. 2016 regarding the implementation of pedagogical approaches mandated by R.A10533 states that the curriculum shall use pedagogical approaches that are constructivist, inquiry-based, reflective, collaborative, and integrative. This was designed to assist all teachers facilitating learner-centered instruction in making the curriculum relevant and in strengthening the teaching and learning process that would rebound to better performance of all learners in any assessment given by the Department of Education. In Digos City Division, in connection with this, teachers continuously put in much effort to teach TLE to make it more interesting and meaningful to every learner by using applicable pedagogical approaches in every lesson. However, it was sad that, as of now, students under Grade 7 and Grade 8 taking exploratory courses in TLE were confused about what particular courses they would take when they reach the next year's level. At their young age, they tend to just pick the easiest one or the available courses offered by the school. Students must rely on what they already know because they were not exposed to the different learning tracks. It was in this context that the researcher came up with this study. The outcomes of this study and the beneficiaries of its findings encompass various stakeholders. Department of Education officials, particularly those in the Sec-

ondary Schools District of Digos City Division, stand to gain insights that may lead to more opportunities for technical assistance to TLE teachers. This assistance aims to capacitate teachers in implementing remedial measures when faced with equipment shortages, while also emphasizing the importance of enhancing laboratory equipment provision to ensure the comprehensive development of learners' lifelong skills. The TLE teachers who participated in this study would benefit from the findings as they reflect on their experiences and challenges in providing remedial measures amidst equipment limitations. This study serves as a foundational reference for their professional development plans. Additionally, the learners involved in this study would gain a clearer understanding of the challenges associated with learning lifelong skills in the absence of equipment. Despite these challenges, learners are encouraged

to maximize their learning potential and master their skills positively. Furthermore, future researchers could build upon this study's findings to explore additional aspects of teaching and learning in TLE. Future studies could offer a more comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon under investigation by conducting further research in various locations and communities. To ensure the comprehensiveness of this study, the following terms are operationally defined. "Remedial measures" pertain to the planned actions taken to address the deficiency or absence of necessary resources or activities (Smith, 2019). The context of this study specifically pertains to the strategies employed by TLE teachers to mitigate the lack of laboratory equipment, which was crucial for effectively delivering the curriculum. These remedial measures allow learners to acquire and refine essential life skills.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of this phenomenological study was to determine teachers' experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights into adopting remedial measures in the absence of teaching equipment. The underlying assumption was that dedicated instruction to develop teachers' reflective competence regarding remedial measures or design would positively shape their attitudes, beliefs, and the performance of the learners. Thus, the unifying element was a focus on reflective activities, embedded whenever possible within a reflective task cycle.

1.2. Research Questions—

- (1) What are the lived experiences of teachers in adopting remedial measures in the absence of equipment in teaching?
- (2) What are the coping mechanisms of the teachers on the challenges they encountered in adopting remedial measures in the absence of equipment in teaching?
- (3) What educational management insights can be drawn from the experiences of the teachers in adopting remedial measures in the absence of equipment in teaching?

1.3. Definition of Terms—Lived Experiences: Refers to the firsthand accounts and personal narratives of teachers as they navigate and respond to the challenges of teaching without adequate equipment. It encompasses their feelings, reflections, and practical actions taken in real-life scenarios.

Remedial Measures: Strategies, actions, or interventions that teachers implement to com-

pensate for the lack of equipment or resources in their teaching environment. These measures aim to bridge the gap and ensure effective teaching and learning despite resource constraints.

Coping Mechanisms: Techniques, behaviors, or psychological strategies that teachers employ to manage and adapt to the stress and difficulties associated with teaching without necessary equipment. These mechanisms help

teachers maintain their effectiveness and well-being in challenging situations.

Challenges: The obstacles, difficulties, and limitations that teachers face when they lack adequate teaching equipment. Challenges can include limited instructional materials, increased workload, and the need for creative problem-solving.

1.4. Significant of the Study—The significance of this study lies in its comprehensive exploration of the lived experiences of teachers who adopt remedial measures in the absence of teaching equipment. By delving into these experiences, the study provides a deep understanding of the innovative and resourceful strate-

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This research study is anchored on the theory of Gunuc’s “Engagement and Technology Integration Theory”. This theory’s main argument is that student success and efficient learning are correlated with academic achievement, and technology use teachers must develop personal and professional competencies such as effective communication, effective presentation, field competence, pedagogical knowledge, knowledge of technology use and competence, and effective classroom management in technology-supported classrooms to integrate technology effectively. Effective technology integration increases and facilitates learning (Gunuc et al., 2018). Bawar (2019) emphasized that adequate instructional facilities, equipment, and materials foster a deeper appreciation of TLE among both students and teachers. Academic achievement is intimately tied to the availability of these instructional resources and is equally influenced by the attitudes, interests, and motivations of students and teachers. Consequently, the failure to meet required competencies often stems from inadequate facilities, leading to compromised

Educational Management Insights: Practical knowledge, observations, and lessons learned from understanding how teachers deal with the absence of equipment. These insights can inform school administrators, policymakers, and educational leaders on how to better support teachers and optimize resource management.

gies that teachers employ to overcome the lack of necessary instructional tools. Investigating the coping mechanisms teachers use to address these challenges offers valuable insights into effective strategies and adaptive practices that can support educators in similar situations, fostering resilience and creativity in the classroom.

academic achievement. Blanca (2019) accentuated the critical role teaching strategies play, especially in boosting student performance. Hence, the selection and application of teaching strategies considerably affect students’ attitudes and class performance. Tingzon and Buyok (2022) identified the struggles faced by teachers tasked with teaching TLE subjects outside their specialized field, compounded by the scarcity of resources and equipment. Moreover, Abella et al. (2021) argued that teaching outside of one’s specialized field can adversely impact both teachers’ and students’ learning outcomes. Another theory of Kolb (1984) described experiential learning as “the process whereby knowledge is created through the transformation of experience. Knowledge results from the combination of grasping and transforming the experience. By participating in experiential learning, students engage in authentic learning experiences that position them as active participants. They develop the ability to bridge the gap between theory and practice and integrate learning beyond the classroom. Experiential learning can increase student engagement, improve learn-

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

ing effectiveness, and enhance work and life skills despite the limited resources in achieving effective learning outcomes. Experiential learning can be used to support students in undertaking learning in a variety of campus-based, project-based, work-integrated, and community contexts. It is beneficial to identify experiences

that students will have an interest in. These experiences should be structured to require the learner to take the initiative, make decisions, and be accountable for results, including learning from natural consequences, mistakes, and successes.

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the research design used, the role of the researcher, the research participants, the data collection and analysis, the trustworthiness, and the ethical considerations. The three most common qualitative methods are participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method is particularly well-matched for gaining a precise type of data. Participant observation was suitable for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their everyday contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) were ideal for collecting data on individuals' histories, perspectives, and experiences, mainly when exploring sensitive topics. The challenging aspect of the research was studying a person's lived experience of a phenomenon in a manner that brings out its universal components (Neubauer et al., 2019). Phenomenology was commonly described as

the study of phenomena as they manifest in our experience, the way we perceive and understand phenomena, and the meaning phenomena have in our subjective experience (Smith, 2018).

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption of this study was the framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret the data collected in a specific field of study. It builds the background utilized for the coming conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated on below. Good research is undertaken with selecting the topic, problem, or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. According to Perera (2018), a research paradigm was a body of generally accepted beliefs and ideas among scientists about how problems might be identified and addressed. It was also a general theory or philosophy. Research paradigms may be called methods in which scientists address the three fundamental concerns of epistemology, ontology, and approach-related queries (Perera, 2018). Ontology. This part of this research study pertains to how the problem relates to the nature of reality. The groundwork for understanding the world in which we occur as people and as members of society was established by ontology, or the study of being. Ontology's potency lies in its ability to reveal our understanding of reality by studying the true nature of things, substances, concepts, experiences, words, and everything (Sol Heng, 2022). This research study explores the realities of understanding teachers' experiences in adopting remedial measures in the absence of laboratory equipment in teaching technology and livelihood education. In this research study, I relied on the voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes and themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The participants' answers in this research study were coded and analyzed to build and construct the commonality and discreteness of responses. I ensured that the participants' responses were cautiously coded to safeguard the reliability of the result. The researcher maintained the authenticity of the responses and precluded from making personal biases as the study progressed. Epistemology refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Epistemology, or the study of knowledge, receives more emphasis in our rationalist society because it explains why we jointly decide that certain things are true and others are not (Sol Heng, 2022). The term originated in the mid-19th century from two Greek words: episteme and logos (Steup Neta, 2020). Episteme can be translated as "knowledge," while logos can be translated as "the study of" (Couper, 2020). In general terms, epistemology is a branch of philosophy that deals with the theory of knowledge. In a more precise way, the Oxford English Dictionary defines epistemology as "the theory of knowledge and understanding, especially about its methods, validity, and scope, and the distinction between justified belief and opinion." I identify phenomenology using thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. On this point, individual researchers "hold explicit belief." This research study aimed to gather crucial information and details on the teachers' experiences in adopting remedial measures in the absence of laboratory equipment to maximize learning outcomes in technology and livelihood education in the Secondary Schools District, Digos City Division. I guaranteed to establish a close interaction with the participants to get firsthand or direct information that would clarify the knowledge underlying the inquiry, especially the teachers' experiences in implementing remedial measures in the absence of laboratory equipment in teaching technology and livelihood education. Axiology refers to

the role of values in research. According to Sol and Heng (2022), in philosophy, axiology refers to a term that deals with ethics, aesthetics, and religion. In research, axiology refers to what the researcher believes is valuable and ethical. I uphold the dignity and value of every information obtained from the participants. The researcher understands the personal and value-laden nature of the information gathered from the study. Therefore, I preserve the merit of the participants' answers and carefully interpret them in light of the participants' interpretations. Rhetorics. This philosophical assumption stressed that I might write in a literary, informal style using my voice, qualitative terms, and limited definitions. In the context of this

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—The methodology is distinct from the method. Essence from a phenomenological research perspective or methodology is described as the intuitive structure of meaning, whereby direct examples build a complex understanding of an experience (Merriam Greiner, 2019). “This form of inquiry is an attempt to deal with inner experience unexamined in everyday life” (Merriam Greiner, 2019). This study unleashed teachers' challenges and coping mechanisms from their narratives. Specifically, those teachers come from the Secondary Schools District, Digos City Division. The researcher's drive to know the deeper meaning of the teachers' experiences in adopting remedial measures without laboratory equipment became the basis for doing this qualitative research study. The challenge is to study a person's lived experience of a phenomenon that highlights the universal essences of that phenomenon (Neubauer et al., 2019), considered helpful in looking for “meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena.” This requires the researcher to suspend his/her attitudes, beliefs, and supposi-

study, I used the first person to explain teachers' experiences in adopting remedial measures in the absence of laboratory equipment and thoroughly discussed their responses during the interview. This concept emerged when social trends neglected emotions, and efforts were on the rise for people's self-assessment. Educationists consider emotional intelligence tests necessary for looking at or predicting people's abilities. So, this field is significant for improving society and knowing the importance of emotions in our daily lives. Advocates of emotional intelligence state that people who know their emotions can spend their lives more quickly and happily, and such types of people are happier than others.

tions to focus on the participant's experience of the phenomenon and identify the essence of the phenomenon. From the definition, human experience is viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not an unreliable source. Phenomenology was a type of research that sought to explain the nature of things through how people experienced them. It translates literally as the “study of phenomena.” In other words, it was the study of the meaning these things (or phenomena) have in the minds of the audience you are studying (Dovetail Editorial Team, 2023). The primary aim of phenomenological research is to gain insight into the experiences and feelings of a specific audience about the phenomenon you are studying. These narratives were the reality in the audience's eyes. They allow you to conclude the phenomenon that may add to or contradict what you thought you knew about it from an internal perspective. Phenomenological research design is handy for topics in which the researcher needs to delve deeply into the audience's thoughts, feelings, and experiences. It was a valuable tool for gaining audience insights, generating awareness about

the item being studied, and developing new theories about audience experience in a specific, controlled situation (Dovetail Editorial Team, 2023).

2.3. Design and Procedure—This study used qualitative research employing phenomenology. Interviews were conducted with individuals with first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. Phenomenology was used in studies that aim to comprehend the fundamental aspects of a particular group of life events experienced by individuals (Creswell Poth, 2018). According to Tenny et al., (2022), the study of the meaning of phenomena or the study of the particular is the precise meaning of phenomenology. Phenomenology's primary goal was to accurately depict, as accurately as possible, the experiences of individuals involved in a phenomenon. The researcher utilized the phenomenological inquiry approach, concentrating on subjective interpretations and prejudices when examining the participant's statements (Juma, 2023). By employing this procedure, the researcher established the significance of the occurrence, circumstance, or experience and acquired a deeper comprehension of the phenomena.

2.4. Research Participants—This study included ten (10) informants as its participants. The selected informants were technology and livelihood education teachers from the Secondary School District, Digos City Division. All the participants were public school teachers from nearby. They were considered individuals who have experienced the phenomenon and can facilitate data collection. The participants have been teaching for at least three (3) years. All the participants came from junior high schools, regardless of age, sex, and marital status. Typically, qualitative data analysis requires a smaller sample size than quantitative data analysis. Before collecting data, qualitative researchers typically need to determine anticipated sample sizes. Estimates are usually required for resource planning objectives, grant applications, and human subjects review committees. Once a study has begun or finished, researchers need to assess if the sample is accurate enough to accomplish the study's goals. Finding a sample that could produce comprehensive and significant results while reducing unnecessary strain on participants and using finite resources, such as time and resources, was a challenge (Young Casey, 2019).

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Considering the nature of qualitative studies, the interaction between researchers and participants could be ethically challenging for the former, as they are personally involved in different stages of the study. Therefore, the formulation of specific ethical guidelines in this respect is essential. The relationship and intimacy established between the researchers and participants in qualitative studies can raise a range of ethical concerns, and qualitative researchers face dilemmas such as respect for privacy, the establishment of honest and open interactions, and avoiding misrepresentations. Every research project has to prioritize the protection of individuals participating by adhering to the relevant ethical principles. Since a qualitative study is so in-depth, ethical issues are especially relevant in this type of research. The current ethical rules for conducting qualitative research, especially when interviewing a vulnerable population of women, frequently focus on broad guidelines rather than

practical application (Mohd Arifin, 2018). The procedures involved in obtaining consent are as follows: it must be provided voluntarily (voluntary), the subjects must understand what is expected of them, and the parties involved must be competent to grant consent. This implies that to take part in a research project; individuals must be fully informed about the study, be able to understand the material, and have the right to choose whether or not to participate. Participants' consent to participate in this study was only acquired following a comprehensive explanation of methodology. Written informed permission was obtained from each participant. Each prospective participant was contacted one-on-one, and the study's objectives and the procedure for gathering data were explained to them. They were provided a suitable time window for any queries or concerns. It was made clear that since participation in the study was entirely up to the participant, refusing to participate or leaving at any point while it was ongoing would not impact them. A participant information document was given to provide more details about the research. The prospective participants were

given enough time—in this example, a week or more—to read the information sheet and determine whether or not they wanted to participate in the study. Before the interview, they had to verify their signature on the informed consent form, which they had to sign to permit them to participate in the study. Potential participants received a clear explanation of their ability to withdraw from the study at any time, even after they had signed the informed consent form. They were also asked permission to record the interview (Arifin, 2018). In this research study, the researcher would follow ethical considerations as part of the qualitative research process. The researcher was responsible for informing the participants completely about the different aspects of the research in incomprehensible language. The needed clarifications include the following issues: the nature of the study, the participants' potential role, the identity of the researcher, the objective of the research, and how the results were published and used. In the same way, this study was submitted to the ethics committee of Rizal Memorial College, a graduate school, for verification and approval.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—The role of the researcher in this study was to attempt to access the thoughts and feelings of study participants. It involves asking informants to talk about things that may be very personal to them. Sometimes, the explored experiences are fresh in the participant's mind, whereas reliving past

experiences may be difficult on other occasions. However, the data are being collected, and the researcher's primary responsibility is to safeguard participants and their data. Mechanisms for such safeguarding must be clearly articulated to participants and approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research begins.

2.7. Data Collection—A closely interrelated step in the process involves determining a strategy for the purposeful sampling of individuals or sites. Once I choose these participants or sites, I must decide on the best methods for gathering data. To do so, I created protocols or written documents, like interviews or obser-

vational guides, for recording the information. Also, I need to anticipate issues of data collection, such as "field issues," which may be a problem along the way, such as having inadequate data, needing to prematurely leave the field or site, or contributing to lost information. Ultimately, a qualitative researcher needs to de-

termine the approach for storing data securely to ensure easy retrieval and safeguarding against potential damage or loss. In this study, there are seven steps in the data collection process. First was the site or individual; the participants were the Technology and Livelihood Education teachers from the Secondary Schools District, Digos City Division. Second is the access and rapport; a letter from the Dean of the Graduate School is given to the graduate student on October 18, 2023, For the approval of the Division Superintendent; a letter of permission for the Schools Division Superintendent on November 29, 2024, The school Principal, and the concerned Technology and Livelihood Education teachers were prepared for easy collection of data on December 20, 2024 The third is the purposeful sampling strategy; all participants have experienced the phenomenon being stud-

ied. Ten (10) informants were selected in this study. The selected teachers were considered individuals who could best inform the researcher about the research problem. They were also considered individuals who have experienced the phenomenon and can facilitate data collection. The fourth was the forms of data, the process of collecting information involved primarily in the Virtual In-Depth Interview (IDI) with the ten (10) informants on December 20, 2023. The fifth was the recording procedures; a protocol was used in the observation and interviewing procedures. A predesigned form was used to record information collected during an observation or interview. The recording and collection of data took place on January 10, 2024 The sixth was the field issues; limited data collection was engaged in this study. The last or the seventh step was the storing of data on April 19, 2014;

2.8. *Data Analysis*—All the collected data underwent thorough examination and thoughtful analysis in this study. Initially, the researcher detailed personal experiences related to the phenomenon being investigated. The researcher commenced by providing a comprehensive account of her encounter with the phenomenon. This effort aimed to separate the researcher's personal experiences, allowing the focus to shift towards the participants. The researcher developed a list of significant statements. Then, finds statements about how the individual was experiencing the topic, lists these significant statements as having equal worth, and works to develop a list of nonrepetitive, nonoverlapping statements. The researcher gathered noteworthy statements and organized them into broader categories of information known as "meaning units" or themes. The researcher outlined what the participants experienced with the phenomenon and detailed how these experiences unfolded. This is called "structural description," the inquirer reflects on the setting and context in

which the phenomenon was experienced. Ultimately, the researcher crafted a comprehensive depiction of the phenomenon by combining textual and structural descriptions. This synthesized portrayal captures the essence of the experience and serves as the pivotal element in a phenomenological study's conclusion. Thematic Content Analysis. The thematic analysis aims to recognize recurring themes within interview data. One benefit of this method is its adaptability. It is suitable for both exploratory studies, where researchers lack predefined patterns, and deductive studies, where researchers have specific interests or hypotheses. Regardless of the study's type or objectives, the crucial aspect of the analysis is that the researcher honors the data and endeavors to portray the interview results with utmost honesty (Mortensen, 2020). Environmental triangulation. Environmental triangulation is applicable solely in studies where specific environmental variables may impact the results. This type of triangulation uses different settings, locations, and other factors, such as the

time, day, and season of the study. The idea was to determine which of these factors influence the information received, and these factors were then changed to see if the findings are the same. The validity can be established if the findings remain unaltered under varying environmental

factors (Naeem, 2019). In this study, triangulation was employed, tailored to the research environment's specific needs, as environmental triangulation was deemed most appropriate for the research context.

2.9. Framework of Analysis—The study's analytical framework was based on Colaizzi's seven-step descriptive phenomenological data analysis method, known for its strength and robustness. Colaizzi's seven-step analysis method provides researchers with clear, logical, and systematic steps (Wirihana et al., 2018; Kwang-Ok et al., 2018). I observed several stages in carrying out thematic analysis. The initial step involved transcribing qualitative data from the tape recordings to gain a better understanding of the data and glean deeper insights. Following Colaizzi's analysis method, I relied on my resources to do the transcription with the use of my personal computer and some reliable headphones. I spent several nights listening to the interviews to expand my understanding of the nuances of the language and semantics of the participants. There was significant variation in practice regarding the establishment of conventions with transcribers. Some negotiated to layout and conventions required, including researchers who wanted the kind of detailed transcriptions appropriate for conversations or narrative analysis. Others were sometimes less directly involved and accepted the conventions generally used by the one transcribing the information. The subsequent stage involves extracting and analyzing the data utilizing manual methods, relying on note-taking and summarization while listening to the recordings. My manual technique usually included some process of verbatim recordings of selected spoken words.

I selected quotations about central issues, or when what was said seemed important or interesting. I employed various methods instructed by my thesis advisor. I annotated transcripts using colored pens and organized data through cutting and pasting. This approach aided me in coding, sorting, and gathering data for analysis. This technique was very useful in understanding links and relationships between issues. All these efforts and procedures included saving verbatim spoken words from the transcripts, which could be cross-referenced to the thematic displays or the maps. In summary, Colaizzi's descriptive phenomenological data analysis method comprises seven steps utilized for analyzing the data. Step 1. I read and re-read all the transcribed interviews to make sense of them; Step 2. I extract significant statements. These are phrases or sentences that directly pertain to the investigated phenomenon; Step 3. The process of giving meaning to the statements. During the process, I broadly categorized pertinent quotes, and subsequently generated themes based on multiple statements that convey similar meanings; Step 4. I repeat steps 1-3 for each interview then I begin to create themes based on the formulated meanings; Step 5. I compile an exhaustive description of everything generated in steps 1-4. Step 6. I summarize the exhaustive description so that there is an identification of the fundamental structure of the phenomenon; Step 7. I ensure the credibility of the data through discussions with experts and independent reviewers.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

Trustworthiness revolves around establishing credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability in qualitative research, trustworthiness holds paramount importance as the outcomes hinge on how the study is conducted by the researcher. The trustworthiness of a research study is crucial for assessing its value. Due to the nature of the qualitative study, honesty in all the data and details is required. Trustworthiness makes the researcher's study worthy to read, share, and be proud of. Credibility refers to the qualitative researcher's confidence in the validity of the research findings. It was a subjective assessment influenced by various factors and perceived by others based on their interactions (Budzowski, 2019). Transferability is the process by which a qualitative researcher shows how the results of the study could be used in different situations. Your responsibility as a researcher is to provide a 'thick description' of the participants and the research process to enable the reader to assess whether your findings were transferable to their setting; this is the so-called transferability judgment. This implies that the reader, not you, makes the transferability judgment because you do not know their specific settings (Korstjens, 2018). Confirmability was the level of objectivity in the study's conclusions. Stated differently, this indicates that participant reactions, rather than the researcher's objectives or potential bias, form the basis of the findings. This means making sure that researcher bias does not alter the interpretation of research participants' comments to support a specific narrative. In this case, the researcher has carefully documented the material utilizing the audit trail, highlighting each data analysis stage to support the choices made. This helps establish that the research study's findings accurately portray participants' responses. Confirmability (objectivity) was the ability of a researcher to evaluate data without bias, including social desirability bias, which could be present from the moment a researcher creates and uses a tool. Keeping reflexivity is essential for controlling this kind of bias (Nyirenda et al., 2020). Dependability was the degree to which the study's results would hold up to replication by different researchers. In other words, someone should be able to duplicate your study using the information in your research report and produce results comparable to those produced by your study. A qualitative researcher could use an inquiry audit to establish dependability, which requires an outside person to review and examine the research process and the data analysis to ensure that the findings are consistent and can be repeated. In this component, the database is very important in backing up information collected and noting changes for all types of research studies. All the data collected must be kept appropriately for future use as references. Dependability, often called consistency, was one of the four standards for rigor and trustworthiness in qualitative research (Janis, 2018).

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter encapsulates insights derived from the real-world experiences of Technology and Livelihood Education instructors. These educators are tasked with embracing novel approaches to enhance teaching despite resource constraints. Additionally, the chapter delves into their strategies for overcoming challenges and implementing effective solutions to ensure curriculum delivery remains impactful. This chapter discussed the themes that emerged from the data gathered. The result primarily presents the description and background of the participants assigned pseudonyms to conceal their identities. Before the discussion, the researcher would like to establish the symbols used as the researcher presents the quotations based on the responses of the study participants.

Regarding the transcriptions of the conducted interviews, the researcher also used codes to refer to the participants of the research.

3.1. The Experiences in adopting remedial measures in the absence of laboratory equipment—Teachers play significant roles in building the highest potential among learners, developing the skills necessary to adapt to the changing demands of society, and improving their knowledge in responding to the needs of the contemporary world. This has been essential in assuring that appropriate information is passed to the learners, making them not only acquire rightful information but indispensable one for living, survival, or its practical applications. The ten permanent junior high school teachers with varying backgrounds from the Digos City Division opined. In conclusion, most TLE teachers were challenged to produce skilled learners who will be globally competent. Considering that DepEd has limited resources to provide sophisticated equipment in all public secondary school laboratories, teachers maximized its potential to deliver the curriculum.

3.1.1. Positive Effects: Develop the Value Positive of Resiliency—Smith et al. (2019) went into greater detail about the resilience-building benefits of improvisation, pointing out that it can help students become more adaptive and resilient as they deal with uncertainty. Furthermore, Lee et al. (2019) observed that students' confidence and self-efficacy were positively impacted by improvisation and that their belief in their talents increased after engaging in improvisational exercises. In their investigation of the emotional intelligence component, Gonzalez et al. (2019) demonstrated how improvisation encouraged students to become more emotionally aware and empathic. These studies suggest that improvisation can offer a range of benefits beyond just learning a performance skill. It can contribute to a well-rounded development by promoting resilience, confidence, and emotional intelligence in students. The value of resiliency lies in its transformative power to promote personal growth, enhance well-being, and foster positive relationships. By embracing resilience, individuals can navigate life's challenges with strength, adaptability, and optimism, ultimately leading to a more fulfilling and meaningful life. These findings supported by Koenig et al. (2019), the use of improvisational teaching strategies was found to be beneficial in promoting student engagement and establishing a dynamic learning environment that encouraged active participation and interaction. Seidel et al. (2019), who discovered that improvisational exercises enhanced students' capacity for critical thought by stimulating their creative thinking and problem-solving abilities, concurred with this sentiment. Glickman et al. (2019) also emphasized the importance of improvisation in helping students acquire critical interpersonal skills by highlighting how it fosters successful communication and teamwork. Researchers indicate that improvisation in the classroom transcends mere entertainment. It serves as a powerful tool, fostering active learning, critical thinking, and valuable interpersonal skills. From boosting engagement and critical thought to nurturing teamwork and communication, improvisation emerges as a multifaceted strategy for promoting well-rounded student development and learning. Johnson (2019) emphasized the significance of improvisational methods in fostering a welcoming and inclusive learning environment where pupils are encouraged to express themselves freely and take intellectual chances. Combining the findings of this research, it is clear that improvisation

in the classroom fosters students' development on multiple levels and enhances their educational experiences while building critical abilities needed for success in a variety of spheres of life. Furthermore, the synthesis of research findings suggests that improvisation in the classroom contributes significantly to students' holistic development. Through improvisational activ-

3.1.2. Collaborating and Resource Sharing—The participants underscored the effectiveness of collaborative planning and curriculum creation in enhancing citation education. Through cooperation, instructors can share best practices, pool resources, and address common issues in teaching citation. This collaborative approach not only facilitates the development of comprehensive and cohesive citation education programs but also fosters interdisciplinary collaboration. Resource sharing played a complementary role in citation education, enabling educators to access a wide array of materials and tools to enhance instruction. In 2019, the proliferation of digital resources and online platforms facilitated the seamless sharing of citation guides, sample papers, instructional videos, and interactive tutorials. These resources, as noted by Brown et al. (2019), provided educators with valuable supplementary materials to reinforce citation concepts and offer students additional support outside the classroom. This proliferation of resources, as highlighted by researcher, empowered educators to supplement their teaching with valuable supplementary materials, thereby reinforcing citation concepts and offering students enhanced learning opportunities beyond the traditional classroom setting. By leveraging these resources, educators were able to create a more dynamic and engaging learning environment, equipping students with the necessary skills and knowledge to excel in their academic endeavors. It is becoming more and more demanded of educators to base their instruction on high-quality evidence. Evidence can

ities, students not only enhance their academic skills but also build critical abilities essential for success in various aspects of life. These activities promote problem-solving, adaptability, communication, and teamwork—skills that are fundamental for navigating the complexities of today's world.

assist teachers in determining the level of understanding that students possess, selecting successful teaching tactics and interventions, keeping track of students' progress, and assessing their efficacy as teachers (Masters, 2018). The utilization of evidence in education is encouraged and made easier by social processes (e.g., Rickinson Edwards, 2021). The researcher emphasizes the pivotal role of evidence in various facets of teaching and learning, including gauging students' comprehension levels, identifying effective teaching strategies and interventions, monitoring student progress, and evaluating teaching efficacy. Furthermore, it highlights the facilitative role of social processes in encouraging and simplifying the utilization of evidence in education. This underscores the importance of evidence-informed practices, not only in enhancing teaching effectiveness but also in improving student outcomes and overall educational quality. Thinking creatively is the process of attempting to observe, learn the laws of things, and deliberately seek out new information to enhance comprehension of the nature of objects and occurrences, as well as identify their causes, stop them, and get rid of the inappropriate and advance the positive (Ton et al., 2020). Furthermore, it is regarded as a technique of reasoning from what has been learned or developed through a relationship with reality, which leads to the utilization of resources to create something new. According to this researcher, this cognitive process extends to identifying the causes of phenomena, mitigating negative outcomes, and advancing positive ones. Addition-

ally, creativity entails reasoning from existing knowledge or experiences gained from engaging with reality. This form of reasoning leads to the utilization of available resources to generate novel ideas and solutions. In essence, cre-

3.1.3. Challenges encountered: Lack of learning equipment—All of the respondents clamored with the lack of learning equipment that they could manipulate and practice in real-life activities. Most of the TLE teachers handled subjects namely, nail care, bread and pastry production, shielded metal arc welding, and electricity. The lack of basic tools made it difficult to see the actual performance of learners. They claimed that many factors are to be considered challenging as to the delivery of subjects such as tools, equipment, and other teaching materials. Supporting this observation, the absence of adequate instructional facilities, equipment, and materials can hinder student and teacher appreciation for Technical-Vocational Livelihood Education (TLE) (Bawar, 2019). This lack of resources can negatively impact academic achievement. While student and teacher attitudes, interests, and motivations are also important factors, research suggests that a lack of proper equipment can be a significant barrier to achieving the required competencies. The researcher emphasizes that while factors like student interest and teacher motivation are important, access to proper equipment is a fundamental building block for success in TLE. By ensuring well-equipped classrooms and workshops, schools can create a more positive learning environment for both students and teachers, ultimately fostering a deeper appreciation for TLE and improving academic achievement. The availability of resources is an important factor to consider when selecting a learning area, as well as the teachers' skills and qualifications. Due to the availability of resources and skill qualification of teachers, schools offer different learning areas of TLE making it more difficult to handle. This becomes a challenge on the part

ativity involves a dynamic interplay between observation, learning, reasoning, and resource utilization, all aimed at fostering innovation and problem-solving.

of the teacher since they need to develop the full potential of the students while having diverse lessons to be formulated, different skills to be performed, and various equipment and facilities to be needed (Zabala, 2018). This researcher underscores the significance of considering resource availability and teacher qualifications when selecting a learning area within Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE). The availability of resources and the skills of teachers play crucial roles in shaping the learning environment and determining the effectiveness of instruction. As schools offer a variety of learning areas within TLE, each requiring specific resources and expertise, teachers face the challenge of managing diverse lessons, skills, and equipment needs. Additionally, the lack of access to the laboratory space, tools, and equipment made it harder for the students to develop the desired abilities necessary for them as TLE major students. The most crucial elements to take into account when working to ensure that students excel in Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) or at a Technical Vocational Institution are instructional materials, tools, and equipment. To become familiar with them, pupils should receive special consideration and top priority (Harina, 2019). This researcher emphasizes the importance of students' access to laboratory space, tools, and equipment in Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) for the development of crucial skills. The lack of these resources presents difficulties for TLE major students, impeding their ability to excel in practical applications and hands-on learning. Thus, guaranteeing the availability of instructional materials, tools, and equipment becomes pivotal in fostering student success in TLE and Technical Vocational Institutions (TVIs).

3.1.4. Lack of training in area of specialization—Technology and livelihood education teachers admitted that they have a difficult time mastering the competencies since the students cannot use the equipment well and do not have the training in teaching using improvised equipment. Sometimes it is difficult to handle subjects like cookery and bread and pastry because they have no competence in this field. They wish they could use household equipment that was improvised. Possibly, they used alternative tools and equipment around the school. The teacher-respondents have to think of activities that could make the learnings of the students more meaningful despite the absence of laboratory equipment, however, they find it difficult because they do not have comprehensive training on the specialization. The narratives from the study participants suggest they face difficulties due to a lack of training in their specialized area of TLE. This aligns with Tan's (2021) research, which emphasizes the need for teachers to develop stronger expertise in their specific TLE subjects. By prioritizing both professional development opportunities and equipping classrooms with adequate resources, institutions can empower TLE teachers to deliver high-quality instruction to their students. This researcher reinforces the importance of teachers enhancing their skills and competence in delivering knowledge to students. Their study emphasizes the critical role of educators in facilitating effective learning experiences. Additionally, the research underscores the need for institutions to address shortages, such as insufficient books, instructional materials, equipment/tools, and other resources, to improve instructional delivery for students. Blanca (2019) accentuated the critical role teaching strategies play, especially in boosting student performance. Hence, the selection and application of teaching strategies considerably affect students' attitudes and class performance. Tingzon Buyok (2022) identified the struggles faced by teachers tasked with teaching TLE subjects outside their specialized field, compounded by the scarcity of resources and equipment. Moreover, Abella et al. (2021) argued that teaching outside of one's specialized field can adversely impact both teachers' and students' learning outcomes. This researcher emphasizes the pivotal role of teaching strategies in enhancing student performance, highlighting the significant impact of strategy selection and application on students' attitudes and classroom achievement. shed light on the challenges encountered by teachers responsible for instructing TLE subjects beyond their specialized expertise, exacerbated by resource and equipment shortages Dela Fuente (2019) emphasized that the incompetence of teachers in teaching makes it difficult and can have negative effects on student performance. missing competence in teaching can affect the quality of instruction and disrupt the connection between the school and impact preparedness for learning. The researcher emphasizes the considerable influence of teacher inadequacy on student performance, indicating that insufficient teaching skills can result in negative outcomes. This lack of competence not only diminishes the quality of instruction but also interrupts the rapport between students and the educational institution, consequently hindering readiness for learning. This observation underscores the crucial necessity of ensuring that educators are equipped with the requisite abilities and proficiencies to successfully guide learning processes and enhance student success

3.1.5. Unrepaired equipment due to limited budget—The provision of laboratory equipment in public schools is limited due to the scarcity of funds from the agency. Most of the teacher-respondents claimed that they used personal money to augment the needed labo-

ratory equipment. The resourceful teachers sometimes asked for help from stakeholders. However, there were instances that they let the learners bring materials they had at home. The significant challenge faced by Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) teachers due to the lack of laboratory equipment, which impedes their ability to effectively impart knowledge to students. Despite this obstacle, the statement emphasizes the importance of teachers being resourceful and innovative in finding alternative solutions to meet students' needs. The narratives suggest that the participants are highly concerned about the proper learning of the students with unprepared equipment due to insufficient funds of the school. This finding is supported by Tan's (2021) study, which highlights the insufficient funding available for the purchase of materials to enhance the curricular offerings. Teachers often invest their resources to fulfill the need for practical applications in the classroom. This researcher sheds light on the inadequacy of funding allocated for the procurement of materials aimed at enriching curricular offerings. This underscores the financial challenges faced by educators in providing comprehensive and engaging learning experiences for their students. The usage of teachers' funds to support the expenses of hands-on learning emerged as one of the innovative solutions teachers implemented to maintain their classes. This approach was backed by a study by Spiegelman (2018) which stated that in the 2014-2015 aca-

demical year, around 94% of public school teachers who participated in the National Teacher and Principal Survey (NTPS) reported spending out of their own pockets. This high prevalence persisted across different school levels, school types, and times. To meet the urgent need for hands-on learning, several measures and innovations were adopted, one of which was the use of teachers' funds to cover the costs of producing a product and delivering positive results for learners. Consequently, teachers invest their own money to meet the need for hands-on applications. The teachers must be flexible, adaptive to change, and predict the essence of the learnings of the students in real-life situations. Gregorio (2018) found that Technology and Livelihood Education teachers have a harder time when it comes to educating students. Even before the pandemic, the significant problem noticed was the lack of education associated with the location of specialization next is that there is no capital funding and enough planning of TLE topics. This researcher discovered that Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) teachers face unique challenges in educating students. Even before the pandemic, significant issues were observed, including insufficient education related to their specialized field, inadequate funding for capital and planning TLE topics, lack of contingency allowances for academic centers and instructional techniques, and challenges in maintaining devices due to budget constraints.

3.2. *Coping mechanisms of the Technology and Livelihood Education teachers on the challenges encountered in adopting remedial measures in the absence of laboratory equipment*—The teachers' adaptability in adopting remedial measures to address the lack of equipment. This may involve implementing alternative teaching methods that do not rely heavily on laboratory equipment, such as utilizing demon-

strations, simulations, or virtual resources to illustrate concepts and principles. By creatively adapting their teaching approaches, TLE teachers ensure that students still receive valuable learning experiences despite the limitations imposed by equipment shortages. The collaborative efforts of TLE teachers in seeking solutions to equipment shortages. This may involve sharing resources and ideas among colleagues, pool-

Fig. 3. Experiences of Technology and Livelihood Education teachers in adopting remedial measures in the absence of laboratory equipment

ing funds or resources to purchase necessary equipment, or engaging with school administrators and parent-teacher associations to advocate for improved resource allocation. This section presents the coping strategies of the technology

and Livelihood Education teachers and the challenges encountered in adopting remedial measures in the absence of laboratory equipment. Their responses were narrowed down into one to generate themes and subthemes.

3.2.1. Being optimistic despite setbacks— As revealed from the interview, the majority of the respondents asked for the support of colleagues and superiors. They were not disappointed easily but rather found ways to perform teaching in a better way. Other stakeholders provide them with the equipment needed because they are happy seeing the students performing their tasks. They also seek support, positive appraisal, planful problem solving, and knowing your priorities. Another consequence of teacher optimism is a deep sense of academic commitment, which forms the cornerstone of effective teaching (Lu, 2021). Teachers' emotions play a significant role in shaping their performance, self-efficacy, job satisfaction, and instructional effectiveness, (Lavy and Eshet, 2018). Given the importance of equipping teachers with the necessary resources to facilitate effective instruction, it is essential to seek support from school administrators and other stakeholders or allocate funds to provide teachers with the equipment needed for optimal teaching and learning experiences. Recognizing this connection, we can explore solutions to support teacher well-being. One approach is to openly communicate these concerns with school heads and other stakeholders. Sharing research on the impact of teacher well-being on student learning can help build a case for addressing their needs. Working collaboratively, we can identify solutions that might involve securing additional resources or equipment. Positive emotions, particularly feelings of joy and love in teaching, have been linked to various positive outcomes in education, including improved per-

formance, enhanced self-efficacy among teachers, the adoption of student-centered teaching approaches, and increased student engagement (Chen, 2019). Additionally, To leverage these positive emotions and promote an enriching educational environment, it may be prudent to seek assistance from school leaders and other stakeholders. Alternatively, investing personal resources to provide necessary equipment and resources could further enhance teachers' experiences and contribute to their overall well-being, thereby fostering a conducive atmosphere for effective teaching and job satisfaction. (Buræ and Moè, 2020). To foster such positive experiences and support teacher well-being, it is imperative to seek assistance from school administrators and other stakeholders. Alternatively, allocating resources to provide teachers with the necessary equipment and resources can help create an environment conducive to positive emotions and effective teaching practices. The spiral effects of emotions have been supported in a daily diary conducted on a sample of teachers, which showed that teachers' daily positive emotions trigger an upward spiral leading to job satisfaction, while negative emotions prompt a downward spiral leading to burnout (Lavy and Eshet, 2018). This research, involving a sample of teachers, demonstrated that positive emotions play a significant role in enhancing job satisfaction. Teachers who maintained a positive outlook experienced an upward spiral effect, leading to increased satisfaction with their jobs. Conversely, those who harbored negative emotions faced a downward spiral, ultimately resulting in burnout.

3.2.2. Becoming technologically savvy—

Utilizing virtual simulations was a good idea in the absence of laboratory equipment. Moreso, conducting thought experiments, and encouraging students to explore real-world applications of concepts can be effective approaches. The majority of the respondents used visual images as a substitute for the real equipment so that their lessons would not be late since there are competencies that teachers need to finish. Through video presentations and presenting pictures of laboratory equipment, some laboratory equipment can be borrowed from other schools or institutions. Collaborative effort to borrow laboratory equipment from other schools or institutions. This reflects a proactive approach to problem-solving, as teachers seek external sources of support to ensure that students have access to the necessary resources for their learning. By reaching out to other educational institutions, teachers not only expand access to equipment but also foster partnerships and collaboration within the broader community. Educational activities have become sustainable in virtually all environments and under virtually all conditions, with interactive whiteboards having long since replaced the traditional blackboard in most schools. Changes emerging today include revised job definitions, changing patterns of daily life, and the desire for economic value; together they represent the primary results of this digital transformation (Lopez et al., 2019). The fast-paced development and changes seen in technology have profoundly affected the teaching process, changing the methods for accessing information as well as the speed at which it is accessed. In this digital age, radical transformations have been seen in educational practices, as in almost every field, and the necessity for educational institutions to keep up with this digital transformation trend is clear. Supporting school administrators as digital leaders and developing professional digital learning opportunities can facilitate the self-development of both teachers and students.

In addition to their many other responsibilities, school leaders need to acquire the necessary knowledge and skills to be effective technology leaders (Karakose Papadakis, 2021). The insight from the researcher emphasizes the pivotal role of school administrators as digital leaders in the modern educational landscape. By supporting school administrators in this capacity and creating professional digital learning opportunities, both teachers and students can benefit from enhanced self-development. In today's educational landscape, it is becoming increasingly important for schools to be technologically adept. As noted by Hobbs and Törner (2019), educators, especially those in Technical and Livelihood Education (TLE), need to have a profound understanding of their subject matter as well as extensive knowledge in their field. In specific area in technology and livelihood education (Grandeza Grandeza, 2024) found a unified utilization of technology in offline and online can enhance students' performance in technology and livelihood education. This highlights the necessity for teachers to be proficient in current technologies and digital tools to improve teaching and learning processes. As emphasized by the researcher, TLE educators, possess a deep understanding of their subject matter is fundamental. However, this is no longer sufficient in isolation. The rapid advancement of technology means that educators must also have extensive knowledge of their field, which includes being adept with current technologies and digital tools. Espinas et al. (2020) highlight the crucial role of contextualized learning modules in the professional development of TVL educators. These modules are tailored to meet the specific needs and contexts of students, making the learning process more relevant and engaging. By aligning educational content with real-world applications and local contexts, these modules enhance the effectiveness of teaching and learning. The researcher discovered the importance of a structured approach that includes the de-

velopment, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation of these modules. This comprehensive strategy ensures that the modules are not

3.2.3. *Contextualizing learning instruction*—Teacher’s proactive approach to addressing challenges related to equipment shortages in the classroom. One insight is the teacher’s willingness to seek help and support from colleagues, recognizing the value of collaboration and teamwork in finding solutions to shared problems. By reaching out to fellow educators, the teacher demonstrates a commitment to leveraging collective expertise and resources to overcome challenges and enhance the learning experience for students. The thematic analysis of the study conforms with the idea of Espinas et. al. (2020) that crafting and developing the contextualized learning modules; implementation; monitoring; evaluation and feedback. As a module, contextualized teaching can be utilized as a training guide for teachers in the Technical-Vocational Livelihood Education strands of the K-12 curriculum. Contextualized teaching, as suggested by the researcher, serves as a valuable training guide for teachers, particularly in the Technical-Vocational Livelihood Education (TVLE) strands of the K-12 curriculum. By tailoring the learning materials to the specific contexts and needs of students, educators can enhance the relevance and applicability of the curriculum. This approach ensures that the content resonates with students’ real-life experiences and future career paths, making learning more engaging and effective. Consequently, according to Hobbs Törner (2019), TLE teachers must have the authority of the subject as well as more extensive knowledge of the field. TLE educators must be engaged to reinforce the professional abilities of TLE students. Moreover, it was emphasized that an educator’s teaching technique is influenced by the content knowledge and academic abilities of the educator, with the

only well-crafted but also effectively integrated into the curriculum, continuously assessed for quality, and improved based on feedback.

quality and the level of their capabilities, considered foremost. However, teaching subjects outside of your expertise is another challenge to look into. One learning approach that can be used is contextual learning or Contextual Teaching and Learning (CTL). Approach Contextual Teaching and Learning (CTL) is a way of presenting lesson material by exposing students to problems that must be solved or resolved to achieve educational goals associated with everyday life. Similar research was also conducted by Komalasari, namely ”Contextual learning has a significant effect on civic skills because it is meaningful for students and develops meaningful learning to develop students’ critical thinking and participative skills in their daily lives ”Which means that applying contextual learning has a significant influence on people’s ability to deal with it because it is natural for students and develops meaningful democratic learning to develop students’ critical thinking and participatory skills in their daily lives. Contextual Teaching and Learning (CTL) is learning that encourages learning activities and learning in the classroom. Selvianiresa in his research showed CTL learning, succeeded in learning using collaborative collaboration with students, high levels of activity in lessons, connections to real-world contexts, and integration of science content with other content and areas of expertise (Dewi Primayana, 2019). This researcher demonstrated the effectiveness of CTL approaches, which involve collaborative learning activities, high levels of student participation, integration of content with real-world contexts, and interdisciplinary connections. By incorporating CTL strategies into instructional practices, educators can create meaningful learning experiences that not only deepen students’ understanding but

Fig. 4. The Emerging Themes of the Coping Mechanisms of the Technology and Livelihood Education Teachers in Adopting Remedial Measures in the Absence of Laboratory Equipment

also enhance their ability to apply knowledge in authentic settings. Education is a process of humanizing humans to be able to actualize themselves in life, whereas good education is education that does not only prepare students for a profession or position but solves the problems they face in daily life. Ideally, education does not only encourage students to develop talents that are tailored to the knowledge acquired at school, but education also aims to improve the quality of human beings who are faithful and fearful of God Almighty, noble, personable, independent, advanced character, tough, smart, creative, skilled, disciplined, work ethic,

professional, responsible, productive, and physically and mentally healthy (Dewi Primayana, 2019). According to this researcher, quality education goes beyond mere preparation for specific careers or roles; it equips students with the skills to address the challenges they encounter in their daily lives. Ideally, education not only fosters the development of students' talents but also seeks to enhance their moral and character development. An effective education instills virtues such as faithfulness, integrity, independence, resilience, creativity, and professionalism.

3.3. *The insights in facilitating exploratory subjects*—The experiences and challenges faced by Technology and Livelihood

Education (TLE) teachers in facilitating exploratory subjects shed light on the resilience, adaptability, and dedication of educators in

overcoming obstacles and providing quality education to students. The importance of creativity and innovation in lesson planning. TLE teachers often encounter challenges such as equipment shortages or lack of resources, but they demonstrate resilience by finding alternative ways to deliver meaningful learning experiences to students. This highlights the resourcefulness and adaptability of educators

3.3.1. Social Development and Contribution to TLE Teachers—Baez-Hernandez (2019) points out that the K to 12 curriculum in the Philippines, with its emphasis on senior high school and technical-vocational (TLE) tracks, has created a surge in demand for TLE teachers. Many industry experts, lacking formal teaching licenses, have been hired on probation to fill this gap. These non-education graduates often take additional education courses to develop the necessary skills to contribute to the social development of their students. For participants, the educator's commitment to experiential learning and community engagement. By encouraging students to apply their skills and knowledge in real-world contexts, the educator fosters a deeper understanding of the relevance and applicability of their learning. Engaging in community projects not only allows students to contribute positively to their communities but also reinforces the importance of social responsibility and civic engagement. In line with this, Tan's (2021) study exemplifies a positive role for students, some non-TLE educators find themselves teaching TLE subjects, even in the absence of comprehensive TLE expertise. While lacking formal TLE training, some have acquired competencies through independent study, peer mentoring, hands-on experience, and leveraging social media and technology resources. However, this scenario not only impacts the educators' instructional capabilities but also potentially infringes upon their professional rights within their em-

in navigating constraints and ensuring that students receive comprehensive instruction in exploratory subjects. This section presents the educational management insights of the participants. Their responses were narrowed down into one to generate themes. These were carefully analyzed and formulated based on what came from informants' accounts and reflections.

ployment context. This researcher's insight underscores the adaptability and resourcefulness of educators who find themselves teaching TLE subjects despite lacking formal training in the field. It highlights the diverse ways in which these educators acquire competencies, including self-directed study, collaboration with peers, and utilization of modern technologies. However, it also raises concerns about the potential limitations of this approach, as educators may not possess the same depth of expertise as those formally trained in TLE. Teachers must be teachers of competent skills with evidence-based knowledge. Since they are considered experts as subjects are in line with their field of specialization, teaching becomes convenient and easy for them (Paragas, 2020). The interactive teaching method has the largest impact on performance among all other teaching strategies. In the teaching process, teachers' timely feedback and formative evaluation provided the greatest impact on the academic output. The academic community attaches great importance to students' autonomous learning, however, self-controlled learning by students themselves may not be an effective way to improve academic output. How the teacher plans and leads the classroom will have a great effect on the student's academic achievement. If a teacher is not fully engaged and excited about what they are teaching, then the children will pick up on this and not be engaged to learn as much as they could be. An effective teacher often

becomes a professional leader who thinks, reflects, and implements (Mella, et. al, 2019). Consequently, since the implementation of the K to 12 Education curriculum in the Philippines highlighting the emergence of senior high schools, the demand for teachers also increases (Baez-Hernandez, 2019). Thus, continuing to develop themselves professionally to enhance their expertise is crucial. Continuing professional development (CPD) means that language teachers need to keep updating their knowledge and skills continuously throughout their careers (Cirocki Farrell, 2019). Following the definition of expertise by Ericsson et al. (2018), teacher expertise is determined by how teachers carry out the tasks in their domain. community partnerships and industry collaborations have played a significant role in enriching TLE education. By forging connections with local businesses, vocational training centers, and government agencies, TLE teachers have been able to provide students with real-world learning op-

3.3.2. *Contingencies for instructional facilities and teaching strategies*—Contingencies for instructional facilities and teaching strategies need evaluation, an approach to measure the educational context to provide a contingencies plan for improvement. Evaluation is a systematic and objective assessment process carried out on activities, projects, programs, strategies, policies, topics, themes, sectors, regions, or operational institutions. As an important part of the policy development process, evaluation provides an accountable and accurate assessment of the relevance, efficiency, effectiveness, impact, and sustainability of the intervention of a program. The emphasis on alignment with teaching strategies reflects a profound understanding within the educational institution of the intricate relationship between pedagogical approaches and logistical support. By prioritizing collaboration with faculty members, the in-

portunities, internships, and access to industry-standard equipment and facilities.. In general, tasks are described as outcomes people are trying to achieve through (sequences of) activities and/or cognitive and affective processes. They are defined with different levels of specificity, ranging from narrow to broad tasks, and there appears to be little consensus regarding the preferred granularity for defining tasks (Ericsson et al., 2018) Focusing on teacher tasks has the advantage that tasks can be defined, observed, and assessed, and are connected to what happens in practice. This strong connection to teaching practice is important given the recent discussions on improving support and recognition for teaching in higher education. The merits of a task-based perspective are demonstrated in at least two domains. In primary and secondary education teaching, core practices are broadly used for educating student teachers (Grossman, 2018).

stitution acknowledges the diverse instructional goals and preferences that shape the learning experience. Rather, the learner is an active constructor of knowledge and a maker of meaning. The role of the teacher becomes one of a facilitator, a guide on the side rather than a dispenser of information, the sage on stage. Moreover, the learners become the active-meaning-make and not the teacher who is imposing the meaning. This means that learners construct their knowledge and understanding of what is taught out of their experiences. Main (2013) showed that learners in constructivist settings exhibited significantly stronger and positive interest and value beliefs about the subject. Also, the results showed initial evidence that while interaction in the context of constructivist literature is important to the learning process, social interaction may not be the only key to better performance. Rather, unlike the social constructivist focus on

Fig. 5. The insights drawn from experiences and challenges encountered by the Technology and Livelihood Education teachers in facilitating exploratory subjects social interaction, interaction with a variety of materials and situations including but not limited to mentors, modules, instruments, probe questions, and peers contribute collectively and positively to the learning experiences of the learners. Moreover, teachers should use teaching approaches that have differential effects on the achievement of students in English. Specifically, constructivist teaching approaches have superior effects on achievement than traditional teaching approaches. These approaches have higher impacts on the retention of the concepts than those who used traditional methodologies.

4. Implications and Future Directions

Presented in this chapter was a brief overview of the study followed by implications based on the findings of the study and future directions in the field of the experiences of Technology and Livelihood Education teachers in adopting remedial measures in the absence of laboratory equipment.

4.1. Findings—The purpose of the study was to explore the experiences of TLE teachers in adopting remedial measures in the absence of laboratory equipment. Through their experiences and feelings, we generate new knowledge for everyone who would understand the struggles of teachers in adopting remedial measures in the absence of laboratory equipment

and extend support when needed. The data were gathered to examine and give meaningful ideas to generate more useful knowledge that would impact the teaching and learning process and the delivery of quality education to our future generation. What enables teachers to thrive despite setbacks, failure, and hardship was the ability to think optimistically in the face of adversity. Optimistic thinking motivates people to continue to persist and to work to find solutions, even when situations look bleak. Teachers' resourcefulness certainly affects learning outcomes. Resourceful teachers were more able to use the most appropriate methods and materials to teach pupils, as they differ in their abilities, prior knowledge, and home backgrounds. The role of teachers is challenged in providing quality education despite its limitations. Ten (10) Technology and Livelihood Education teachers were interviewed. In conclusion, to meet the changing demands of teachers in adopting remedial measures in the absence of laboratory equipment. However, high-quality teachers were capable and willing to continually learn and re-learn their trade. This learning of skills has

4.2. Implications—The analysis revealed that the emerging themes of the TLE teachers in coping with the challenges of adopting remedial measures to continue teaching in the absence of laboratory equipment were being optimistic despite setbacks, becoming technologically savvy, and contextualizing learning instruction. Optimism matters, and it could be learned. Teachers could lay the foundation for happiness, resilience, and success by teaching their students how to think optimistically, especially when the situation is challenging. In addition, teachers' resourcefulness certainly affects learning outcomes. Resourceful teachers were more able to use the most appropriate methods and materials to teach pupils, as they differ in their abilities, prior knowledge, and home back-

grounds. It was evident that, if ICTs were used appropriately to support teaching and learning in schools and colleges, they could be an effective tool, particularly in improving the quality of content and pedagogy. Many academic institutions were now using videos, interactive television, and computer programs in the teaching and learning processes. The Internet has turned into a wide and resourceful source of information for learners and trainers around the world. The Technical-Vocational Livelihood Education strategies and indicators are the strategic procedures needed to come up with well-informed contextualized learning instruction. A study resulted in the seven stages of a contextualized teaching module which include planning; assessment of the curriculum guide and resources;

become a high priority in public schools. There were three themes where TLE teachers narrated their experiences in adopting remedial measures in the absence of laboratory equipment: lack of learning equipment, lack of training in area of specialization, and outsourcing of funds for equipment. Technical and vocational education means hands-on education. The rationale of technical and vocational education is to prepare people to work as technologists. The purpose of vocational and technical training is to provide the individual to enter a job in the business and to gain basic behaviors to improve. Technical-Vocational Livelihood education syllabus was designed to provide the essential fundamental knowledge and the analytical, practical, and experimental skills necessary for a lifelong career. Meanwhile, for effective teaching and learning of Technical-Vocational Livelihood (TVL) education, instructional materials and facilities are necessary. Instructional materials and facilities help to facilitate teaching and learning and are used to influence concrete and permanent changes in technical behavior.

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collaboration and consultative meeting; crafting and developing of the contextualized learning modules; implementation; monitoring; and evaluation and feedback. As a module, contextualized teaching could be utilized as a training guide for teachers in the Technical-Vocational Livelihood Education strands of the K-12 curriculum. Lastly, the educational management insights drawn from TLE teachers' experiences in adopting remedial measures in the absence of laboratory equipment were as follows: developing teachers' expertise and contingencies for instructional facilities and teaching strategies. Teachers must be teachers of competent skills with evidence-based knowledge, capable of teaching the subjects not by familiarity or because no one else accepts handling the subject but with expertise and specialization. Since they were considered experts as subjects were in line with their field of specialization, teaching became convenient and easy for them when they were in their comfort zone; they tended to be more productive and motivated and further experienced lesser stress or burnout, teacher retention, and turnover. Teacher education was based on sincerity, passion, and love for students and the profession. Teachers are seen to play significant roles in building the highest potential among learners, developing the skills necessary to adapt to society's changing demands, and im-

proving their knowledge in responding to the needs of the contemporary world. This has been essential in assuring that appropriate information is passed to the learners, making them not only acquire rightful information but indispensable one: for living, survival, or its practical applications. Teachers must be teachers of competent skills with evidence-based knowledge, capable of teaching the subjects not by familiarity or because no one else accepts handling the subject but with expertise. Also, the results showed initial evidence that while interaction in the context of constructivist literature is important to the learning process, social interaction may not be the only key to better performance. Rather, unlike the social constructivist focus on social interaction, interaction with a variety of materials and situations, including but not limited to mentors, modules, instruments, probe questions, and peers, contribute collectively and positively to the learning experiences of the learners. Moreover, teachers should use teaching approaches that have differential effects on students' achievement in English. Specifically, constructivist teaching approaches have superior effects on achievement than traditional teaching approaches. These approaches have higher impacts on concept retention than those who used traditional methodologies.

4.3. Future Directions—Teachers facing the absence of equipment often undergo a range of lived experiences that shape their pedagogical approach and resilience. Initially, they feel frustrated and disappointed as they realize the limitations imposed by the lack of essential tools for effective instruction. However, these challenges prompt a surge of creativity and innovation as teachers improvise alternative teaching methods using readily available resources. This process fosters a spirit of collaboration among educators, who share ideas and materials to overcome

equipment shortages collectively. Teachers employ various coping mechanisms to navigate the challenges they encounter when adopting remedial measures in the absence of equipment in teaching. Firstly, they lean on their professional networks for support, seeking advice and sharing strategies with colleagues facing similar circumstances. This collaboration not only provides practical solutions but also fosters a sense of camaraderie and solidarity among educators. Additionally, teachers often tap into their creativity, leveraging alternative teaching methods

and materials to deliver engaging lessons despite equipment limitations. They may integrate technology, utilize everyday objects creatively, or design interactive activities that stimulate student learning. The experiences of teachers in adopting remedial measures in the absence of equipment offer valuable insights for educational management. It underscores the importance of resource allocation and planning. Educational institutions must prioritize equipping classrooms and laboratories with the necessary tools and materials to support effective teaching and learning. Adequate funding and strategic resource allocation can help prevent situations where teachers were forced to adopt remedial measures due to equipment shortages. These experiences highlight the need for ongoing professional development and support for teachers. Training programs that focus on creative teaching strategies, improvisation techniques, and technology integration can better prepare educators to adapt to unexpected challenges. Additionally, establishing a culture of collaboration and knowledge sharing among teachers fosters resilience and innovation in problem-solving.

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